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Tumor-intrinsic natural killer KIR gene methylation correlates with survival in breast cancer.

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We measured differences in DNA methylation globally in the tumor genome when comparing patients based on outcome (survival). We identified methylation of genes encoding natural killer KIR receptors when comparing total transcription in tumors with inferior and superior survival. Killer cell processes are likely active during breast cancer and influence organismal outcomes like patient survival.